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SYNTHESIS OF POTENTIAL CORROSION INHIBITORS BASED ON QUATERNARY SALTS OF PYRIDE-CONTAINING AMIDES AND UREAS

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Abstract

A method for the synthesis of quaternary salts of mono- and diquaternized N-arylnicotinamides and ureas as potential inhibitors of acid corrosion is proposed. Available reagents were used in the syntheses: benzyl chloride, allyl bromide, nicotinic acid chlorides, aromatic amines and isocyanates. Preparative yields are 67-87%.

Keywords: corrosion inhibitors, quaternary ammonium salts, N-arylnicotinamides, quaternized and diquaternized salts, quaternized salts based on nicotine-containing ureas.

Materials and methods

IR spectra of the synthesized compounds in KBr tablets were recorded on a Specord-75-JR instrument. PMR spectra were obtained on a JEOL spectrometer (90 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ and CDCl₃, chemical shifts were measured in the δ -scale.

N-phenylnicotinamide (9). Dissolve 4 g (0.043 mol) of aniline 6 in 50 ml of dichloroethane, add 12.06 ml (0.086 mol) of triethylamine and 7.6 g of hydrochloric acid (0.043 mol). After boiling for 7 h, wash twice with a dilute solution of soda and three times with water. Dry with sodium sulfate. Filter, wash the precipitate with chloroform. Remove the solvent. Add 250 ml of methanol and activated carbon to the precipitate, boil for 10-15 min. The resulting solution is filtered and the solvent is evaporated under vacuum. The precipitate is recrystallized from acetone. Yield 4.94 g (58%). M.p. = 127°C.

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3365 (NH), 1705 (C=O).

¹H NMR (δ , m.p., CDCl₃): 8.43 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.05 (1H, d., j = 1.0 Hz), 8.70 (1H, d., j = 4.0 Hz), 8.16 (1H, d.d., j = 6.0 Hz, j = 1.0 Hz), 7.62-7.14 (m., 6H).

3-(N-phenylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride (12). Dissolve 4.94 g (0.025 mol) of amide 9 in 50 ml of benzene (dry) and add 2.86 ml (0.025 mol) of benzyl chloride. The mixture is boiled for 6 hours and cooled. Then the precipitate is filtered off and washed several times with dry benzene to completely remove benzyl chloride. Dry in air. Yield 5.98 g (74%). Mp = 119°C.

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3340 (NH), 1700 (C=O).

¹H NMR (δ , m.p., DMSO-d₆): 3.28 (2H, c., CH₂), 10.29 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.17 (1H, d., j = 1.0 Hz), 8.74 (1H, d.d., j = 4.0 Hz, j = 1.0 Hz), 8.30 (1H, d.d., j = 6.0 Hz, j = 1.0 Hz), 7.73-7.08 (m., 11H).

1-Naphthylnicotinamide (10). Dissolve 4 g (0.028 mol) of 1-naphthylamine 7 in 50 ml of dichloroethane, add 7.8 ml (0.056 mol) of triethylamine and 5 g of hydrochloric acid (0.028 mol). After boiling for 7 h, wash twice with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and three times with water. Dry with sodium sulfate. Filter, wash the precipitate with chloroform. Remove the solvent. Add 250 ml of methanol and activated carbon to the precipitate, boil for 10-15 min. The resulting solution is filtered and the solvent is evaporated under vacuum. The precipitate is recrystallized from acetone. Yield 3.53 g (51%). M.p. = 136°C.

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3310 (NH), 1635 (C=O).

¹H NMR (δ , m.p., CDCl₃): 8.26 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.20 (1H, d., j = 1.0 Hz), 8.79 (1H, d.d., j = 1.0 Hz, j = 4.0 Hz), 8.26-7.51 (m., 9H).

3-(N-1-naphthylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride (13). Dissolve 3.53 g (0.012 mol) of amide 10 in 30 ml of benzene (dry) and add 1.632 ml (0.012 mol) of benzyl chloride. The mixture is boiled for 5.5 hours and cooled. Then the precipitate is filtered off and washed several times with dry benzene to completely remove benzyl chloride. Dry in air. Yield 3.57 g (67%). M.p. = 128°C.

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3340 (NH), 1680 (C=O).

¹H NMR (δ , m.ch., DMSO-d₆): 3.71 (2H, c., CH₂), 10.61 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.10 (1H, d., j = 1.0 Hz), 8.75 (1H, d.d., j = 4.0 Hz, j = 1.0 Hz), 8.49-7.48 (m., 14H).

2-Naphthylnicotinamide (11). Dissolve 4 g (0.028 mol) of 2-naphthylamine 8 in 50 ml of dichloroethane, add 7.8 ml (0.056 mol) of triethylamine and 5 g of hydrochloric acid (0.028 mol). After boiling for 7 h, wash twice with a dilute solution of soda and three times with water. Dry with sodium sulfate. Filter, wash the precipitate with chloroform. Remove the solvent. Add 250 ml of methanol and activated carbon to the

precipitate, boil for 10-15 min. The resulting solution is filtered and the methanol is evaporated under vacuum. The precipitate is recrystallized from acetone. Yield 3.04 g (44%). M.p. = 161°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3250 (NH), 1625 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.h., CDCl_3): 8.43 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.12 (1H, d., $j = 1.0$ Hz), 8.73 (1H, d.d., $j = 1.0$ Hz, $j = 4.0$ Hz), 8.28-7.31 (m., 9H).

3-(N-2-Naphthylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride (14). Dissolve 3.04 g (0.012 mol) of amide 11 in 30 ml of benzene (dry) and add 1.376 ml (0.012 mol) of benzyl chloride. The mixture is boiled for 5.5 h and cooled. Then the precipitate is filtered off and washed several times with dry benzene to completely remove benzyl chloride. Dry in air. Yield 3.3 g (72%). M.p. = 148°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3350 (NH), 1670 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.ch., $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 3.52 (2H, c., CH_2), 10.80 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.23 (1H, d., $j = 1.0$ Hz), 8.84 (1H, d.d., $j = 4.0$ Hz, $j = 1.0$ Hz), 8.54-7.41 (m., 14H).

3-(N-2-Naphthylcarboxamido)-N-allylpyridinium bromide (17). Dissolve 3.82 g (0.0154 mol) of amide 11 in 50 ml of benzene (dry) and add 1.33 ml (0.0154 mol) of allyl bromide. The mixture is boiled for 16 h and the solvent is removed. The product is washed with benzene and crystallized from methanol. Yield 4.03 g (71%). M.p. (dec.) = 283°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3350 (NH), 1685 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.h., $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 5.85 (2H, c., CH_2), 8.10 (1H, s.s., NH), 6.01-7.95 (m., 14H).

3-(N-phenylcarboxamido)-N-allylpyridinium bromide (18). Dissolve 12.27 g (0.062 mol) of phenylnicotinamide 9 in 60 ml of benzene (dry) and add 5.4 ml (0.062 mol) of allyl bromide. The mixture is boiled for 10 h. A precipitate forms, which is filtered and dried in air. The product is crystallized from ethanol. Yield 16.4 g (83%). M.p. (dec.) = 221°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3350 (NH), 1695 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.ch., $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 5.46 (2H, c., CH_2), 8.39 (1H, s.s., NH), 6.28-7.88 (m., 12H).

5-Bromo-2-benzoylamino-N-allylpyridinium bromide (19). Dissolve 6.67 g (0.024 mol) of 5-bromo-2-benzoylamino pyridine 16 in 50 ml of benzene (dry) and add 2.1 ml (0.024 mol) of allyl bromide. The mixture is boiled for 16 h and the solvent is removed. The residue is washed with benzene and crystallized from methanol. Yield 7.28 g (76%). M.p. (dec.) = 238°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3330 (NH), 1650 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.ch., $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 8.29 (2H, c., CH_2), 8.94 (1H, s.s., NH), 7.54-7.87 (m., 11H).

N-(2-pyridyl)nicotinamide (25). Dissolve 1.03 g (0.011 mol) of 2-aminopyridine 22 in 50 ml of chloroform (dry), add 3.09 ml (0.022 mol) of triethylamine and 2 g (0.011 mol) of hydrochloric acid. After 8 h of boiling, cool and wash with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. Then the residue is recrystallized from benzene. Yield 0.9 g (41%). M.p. = 144°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3200-2910 (NH), 1650 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.h., CDCl_3): 9.36 (H5, s.s., NH), 9.14 (H1, d., $j_{1,4} = 1.5$ Hz), 8.75 (CH_2 , d.d., $j_{2,3} = 4.5$ Hz, $j_{2,4} = 1.5$ Hz), 8.31-8.12 (m., H6, H9), 7.74 (H8, $j_{8,9} = 6.5$ Hz, $j_{8,9} = 1.5$ Hz), 7.40 (H3, d.d., $j_{3,4} = 6.5$ Hz, $j_{3,2}$

= 4.5 Hz), 7.29 (H4, d., $j_{4,3} = 6.5$ Hz), 7.04 (H7, d.d., $j_{7,8} = 6.5$ Hz, $j_{7,6} = 4.0$ Hz).

3-(N-(2-pyridyl)carboxamido)pyridyl-N,N-dibenzylpyridinium chloride (28). Dissolve 2.33 g (0.012 mol) of amide 25 in 50 ml of benzene (dry) and add 2.75 ml (0.024 mol) of benzyl chloride. The mixture is boiled for 16 hours and cooled. Then the reaction mixture is filtered and dried in air. Yield 1.78 g (33%). M.p. (dec.) = 129°C.

^1H NMR (δ , m.h., CDCl_3): 9.44 (3H, m.s., NH, CH_2), 8.22 (7H, m., CH_2 , Ph), 7.03 (3H, m., Ph), 7.38 (3H, m., Ph, Py), 7.74 (2H, m., Py), 8.76 (2H, m., Py), 9.18 (3H, m., Py).

N-4-pyridylnicotinamide (26). Dissolve 3 g (0.03 mol) of 4-aminopyridine 23 in 50 ml of chloroform (dry), add 8.4 ml (0.06 mol) of triethylamine and 5.4 g (0.03 mol) of hydrochloric acid. After 6 h of boiling, the reaction mixture is cooled and treated with a dilute solution of NaOH (10%), washed with water until neutral and dried with sodium sulfate. Then the chloroform is evaporated. Yield 4.82 g (38%). M.p. = 186°C.

^1H NMR (δ , m.p., CDCl_3): 9.51 (1H, s.s., NH), 8.32 (2H, d., $j = 6.0$ Hz), 8.11 (1H, s.), 7.83 (1H, d., $j = 6.5$ Hz), 7.57 (2H, d., $j = 6.0$ Hz), 7.52-7.28 (2H).

3-(N-(4-pyridyl)carboxamido)pyridyl-N,N-dibenzylpyridinium chloride (29). Dissolve 4 g (0.02 mol) of amide 26 in 50 ml of benzene (dry) and add 4.59 ml (0.04 mol) of benzyl chloride. The mixture is boiled for 16 hours and cooled. Then the reaction mixture is filtered and dried in air. Yield 2.99 g (44%). M.p. (dec.) = 174°C.

^1H NMR (δ , m.h., CDCl_3): 9.63 (3H, s.s., NH, CH_2), 8.52 (2H, d., $j = 6.5$ Hz), 8.24 (m., 7H), 7.87 (2H, d., $j = 6.5$ Hz), 7.29 (m., 7H), 5.91 (2H, s., CH_2).

N-3-quinolylnicotinamide (27). Dissolve 3.97 g (0.027 mol) of 3-aminoquinoline 24 in 100 ml of chloroform (dry) and add 4.9 g (0.027 mol) of hydrochloric acid. After 9 hours of boiling, a precipitate forms, which is filtered off and dissolved in a minimum amount of water. Then, excess KOH is added, a precipitate forms upon cooling. After that, the substance is filtered off and dried in air. Yield 4.06 g (62%). M.p. = 152°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3330-3050 (NH), 1640 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.p., CDCl_3): 9.87 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.13 (1H, s., CH), 8.92 (1H, s., CH), 8.34 (1H, d., $j = 6.0$ Hz), 7.94-7.41 (m., 7H).

3-(N-(3-quinolyl-N-benzylquinolilium chloride)carboxamido)pyridyl-N-benzylpyridinium chloride (30). Dissolve 3.56 g (0.014 mol) of amide 27 in 100 ml of chloroform (dry) and add 3.21 ml (0.028 mol) of benzyl chloride. After boiling for 10 hours, the chloroform is evaporated. Yield 6.23 g (87%). M.p. (with decomp.) = 136°C.

^1H NMR (δ , m.p., $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 10.19 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.44 (2H, s.s., CH_2), 8.10-7.42 (m., 13H), 6.05 (2H, s., CH_2).

N¹-(2-pyridyl)-N¹-(phenyl)urea (31). Dissolve 5.0 g (0.05 mol) of 2-aminopyridine 22 in 50 ml of benzene (dry) and add 5.7 ml (0.05 mol) of isocyanate. The reaction occurs instantaneously upon heating – a white precipitate is formed. Then the reaction mixture is

filtered, the precipitate is dried in air. Yield 10.83 g (96%). M.p. = 192°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3200-2910 (NH), 1690 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.h., CDCl_3): 11.31 (1H, s.s., NH), 10.21 (1H, s., NH), 8.21 (1H, d., $j = 7.7$ Hz), 7.75-6.93 (m., 8H).

N'-(2-pyridyl)-*N*-benzylpyridinium chloride)-*N''*-(phenyl)urea (33). Dissolve 5.0 g (0.0235 mol) of urea 31 in 27 ml (0.2354 mol) of benzyl chloride and boil for 20 hours. Next, extract by mixing the reaction mass with water and methylene. Then, evaporate the water from the aqueous layer. Yield 4.72 g (59%). M.p. (dec.) = 179°C.

^1H NMR (δ , m.p., CDCl_3): 10.45 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.20 (1H, s.s., NH), 7.93 (1H, d., $j = 6.8$ Hz, CH_2), 7.50-6.71 (m., 14H), 4.57 (1H, d., $j = 6.8$ Hz, CH_2).

N'-(4-pyridyl)-*N''*-(phenyl)urea (32). Dissolve 5.0 g (0.05 mol) of 4-aminopyridine 25 in 50 ml of chloroform (dry) and add 5.7 ml (0.05 mol) of isocyanate. After 8 hours of boiling, the chloroform is evaporated and the product is dried in air. Yield 11.15 g (99%). M.p. = 247°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3270-2960 (NH), 1800 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.c., CDCl_3): 8.50 (1H, br.s., NH), 8.25 (2H, d., $j = 6.4$ Hz), 7.63-6.93 (m., 8H).

N'-(4-pyridyl)-*N*-benzylpyridinium chloride)-*N''*-(phenyl)urea (34). Dissolve 11.27 g (0.053 mol) of urea 32 in 120 ml of chloroform (dry), add 6.08 ml (0.053 mol) of benzyl chloride and boil for 10 hours. Then the resulting substance is filtered off and left to dry in air. Yield 13.82 g (77%). M.p. (dec.) = 225°C.

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3270-2960 (NH), 1750 (C=O).

^1H NMR (δ , m.ch., CDCl_3): 11.91 (1H, s.s., NH), 9.58 (1H, s.s., NH), 8.40 (2H, d., $j = 7.0$ Hz), 8.02 (2H, d., $j = 7.0$ Hz), 7.67-6.95 (m., 10H), 5.49 (2H, p., CH_2).

Results and discussion.

The search for effective adsorption inhibitors of acid corrosion of metals and bactericidal preparations

is an urgent task. The compounds used to create the specified industrial reagents include quaternary ammonium salts. For example, it is known [1] that the greatest anti-corrosion effect is exhibited by such quaternary ammonium salts, in the structure of which, in addition to the adsorption center - the quaternary nitrogen atom - there are several adsorption centers of different types: nitrogen atoms with a free pair of electrons, oxo groups, which are characterized by donor-acceptor interaction with the metal surface. The creation of such additional adsorption centers allows obtaining compounds, the action of which as corrosion inhibitors can be enhanced by combining several inhibitory effects. Quaternary ammonium salts are also part of disinfectants for medical and household purposes [2]. It is known that quaternary salts of the pyridine series have a wide range of useful properties. First of all, it is necessary to emphasize their use in technological processes as inhibitors of acid corrosion of metals and antimicrobial drugs [3, 4]. For the development of new promising technologies, it is necessary to develop measures to protect metals from corrosion, and the emergence of resistance in microorganisms to existing bactericides requires the use of new, more effective disinfectants. In this regard, it becomes important to obtain new quaternary salts of the pyridine series, which have the specified properties, based on available and cheap reagents.

1. Synthesis of monoquaternized amides

N-phenylnicotinamide 9, 1-naphthylnicotinamide 10 and 2-naphthylnicotinamide 11 were obtained by acylation of aniline 6, 1-naphthylamine 7 and 2-naphthylamine 8 with nicotinic acid chloride, respectively. For the experiments, reagents of the "pure" brand were used. Quaternization of 9-11 with benzyl chloride was carried out in benzene, the yield of salts 12-14 was 67-74%

The synthesized salts were purified by recrystallization from benzene. Confirmation of the structure of salts 12-14 was carried out using IR and PMR spectra. Absorption bands characteristic of the amide group are present in the IR spectra at frequencies of 3340-3350 and 1670-1700 cm^{-1} . In the PMR spectra of these salts

there are signals of protons of the NH group at 10.29-10.75 m.p. and methylene protons of the benzyl radical at 3.28-3.71 m.p.

The following substituted N-allylpyridinium bromides were also synthesized:

signals of the NH N-arylnicotinamides 11 and 9 were synthesized by acylation of aniline and 2-naphthylamine with nicotinic acid chloride in benzene. Benzoylaminopyridine 16, required for quaternization, was obtained by boiling a mixture of benzoyl chloride and the corresponding amine in a 1 : 1 ratio in chloroform and purified by recrystallization from benzene. Allyl bromide was used for quaternization of N-arylnicotinamides 11 and 9.

Quaternization of benzoylaminopyridine 16 with allyl bromide was carried out by boiling in benzene.

The structure of the compounds was confirmed by IR and PMR spectra. Absorption bands characteristic of the amide group appear in the IR spectra at 1650-1695 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 3330-3350 (NH) cm^{-1} . The PMR spectra contain -group proton at 8.1-8.9 ppm, methylene protons of the allyl radical at 5.24-5.9 for salts 17 and 18 and at 8.3 for salt 19.

The synthesis of substituted N-allylpyridinium halides was carried out according to the general scheme:

2. Synthesis of diquaternized amides

N-2-pyridylnicotinamide 25, N-4-pyridylnicotinamide 26 and N-3-quinolylnicotinamide 27 were obtained by acylation of 2-aminopyridine 22, 4-aminopyridine 23 and 3-aminoquinoline 24 with nicotinic acid chloride, respectively. Quaternization of 25-27 with benzyl chloride was carried out in benzene or chloroform. The yield of the synthesized salts 28-30 is 33-87%.

Confirmation of the structure of salts 28-30 was carried out using PMR spectra. Characteristic signals of protons of the NH group at 9.44-10.19 ppm and methylene protons of the benzyl radical at 9.44-6.05 ppm are present. The latter is possibly explained by the fact that the mutual influence of protons of CH₂ groups leads to their shift into a weaker field.

3. Synthesis of urea-based salts

N[']-(2-pyridyl)-N^{''}-(phenyl)urea 31 and N[']-(4-pyridyl)-N^{''}-(phenyl)urea 32 were obtained by the interaction of phenylisocyanate with 2-aminopyridine 22 and 4-aminopyridine 25, respectively. "Pure" reagents

were used for the experiments. Quaternization of 31 and 32 with benzyl chloride was carried out in chloroform, the yield of salts 33 and 34 was 59-77%.

The structure of salts 33 and 34 was confirmed by IR and PMR spectra. In the PMR spectra of these salts there are signals of protons of the NH group at 11.91-9.20 m.p. and methylene protons of the benzyl radical at 7.93-4.57 m.p. Absorption bands characteristic of the diamidocarbonate group are present in the IR spectrum of salt 34 at frequencies of 3270-2960 (NH) and 1750 (C=O) cm⁻¹.

Conclusions

1. A method for the synthesis of quaternary salts of mono- and diquaternized N-arylnicotinamides and ureas as potential inhibitors of acid corrosion is proposed. Available reagents were used in the syntheses: benzyl chloride, allyl bromide, nicotinic acid chlorides,

aromatic amines and isocyanates. Preparative yields are 67-87%.

2. All synthesized substances will be tested as corrosion inhibitors and antibacterial drugs.

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